

THE IMAGE OF HISTORICAL PERSONS IN THE WORKS OF MIRKARIM ASIM

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Annotation: This article analyzes the artistic interpretation of historical figures in the work of Mirkarim Osim. The author's skill in creating an image while preserving historical truth is revealed. In the work of Mirkarim Osim, the image of a historical figure serves as an artistic means of understanding national identity. The writer's skill lies in the fact that he was able to transform dry information from historical sources into an aesthetic phenomenon. His works serve as a benchmark for Uzbek literature in terms of the transformation of historical truth into artistic truth.

Keywords: historical figure, Alisher Navoi, Tomaris, Spitamen, era, story, tale.

INTRODUCTION

The historical works of Mirkarim Osim, one of the brightest representatives of Uzbek literature of the 19th century, on the social and political life of historical figures, made a fundamental change in Uzbek literature. The writer began his work by writing poems, but later he also created reference books and textbooks on history. Mirkarim Osim wrote historical works about a number of scholars, such as Tomaris, Temur Malik, Alexander, Alisher Navoi, Beruni, Khorezm. The purpose of this article is to analyze how historical figures are depicted in the writer's works, their character and means of artistic expression. The works on historical-heroic themes include Tomaris, Shirok, Iskandar and Spitamen, Mahmud Torobi, Otrar, and Temur Malik; the works on historical-domestic themes include On the Caravan Roads (Ambassadors), The Ambassador of Khorezm (Swallows of Friendship), Light and

Darkness (Memorial of the Heart), and Mohlaroyim and Khanposhsha; the works on historical-biographies include Clouds over Jaihun, Ibn Sina's Story, The Journey of the Stars, Light in the Darkness, and Broken Setor.

Discussion.

The works of the historian should be studied in three groups according to their periods:

1. Stories about the ancient periods of our history (Arab Caliphate, Iranian kings, Alexander the Great).
2. Works telling about the history of the Middle Ages (Biographies of cultural figures, stories and stories, Mongol invasion and science).
3. Works about the historical life of the period from the 17th century to the October Revolution. Also, the works of Mirkarim Asim can be analyzed according to three large thematic groups:

1. Works on the theme of historical heroism
2. Works on historical-domestic themes
3. Historical biographical works Works on the theme of historical heroism:

“O‘trar”, “Temur Malik”, “Alexander and Spitamen”, “To‘maris”.

Works on domestic themes:

“Caravan bells”, “Ambassadors”, “Mohlaroyim and Khanposhsha”.

“Singan Setor” (Mashrab),

“Zulmat ichra nur” (Navoi),

“Abu Sino’s story”,

“Clouds over Jaikhun” (Beruni),

“The birth of Algebra” (Khwarizmi).

In particular, the writer’s stories “Zulmat In the passage called "The Language of Birds" in the work "Ichra Nur" it is told that young Alisher read Sharafiddin Ali Yazdiy's book "Mantiq ut-tayr" without letting go and memorized every page of it. This can be explained by the fact that the writer is a very honest writer, who presents the stories about Alisher Navoi in the form of small fragments. In addition, in other works of the writer, such as "Tu'maris", "Temur Malik", "Alexander and Spitamen", "The Story of Ibn Sina", "Clouds over Jaykhun", the writer's portraits of historical figures can be imagined through the concise use of modern, artistic interpretations. Professor, literary critic Ozod Sharafiddinov highly evaluates Mirkarim Asim's artistic interpretation of history, the boundlessness of our history, and the realistic depiction of great figures: "Mirkarim Asim is one of the writers who created a unique

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The images of historical figures in Mirkarim Asim's works are created on the basis of deep artistic analysis. The results of the study showed that he revives historical truth not only as a fact, but also through human experiences and psychological images. The writer's works are of great importance in educating the younger generation, instilling in them a spirit of love for our great ancestors, and in glorifying the ideals of patriotism and humanity. The works written with the efforts of scientific institutions in the improvement of national spirituality have an incomparable place.

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Story of Ibn Sina", "The Journey of the Stars" are considered to be among the works that satisfy the spiritual need. In these works, Mirkarim Asim tells the story of his

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world-famous discoveries. In the short story "The Birth of Algebra", created in 1983

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on the eve of the 1200th anniversary of Muhammad al-Khwarizmi, a literary portrait

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of the great mathematician and his world-famous discoveries in mathematics were skillfully depicted.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE AND SOURCES. MAIN SOURCES (LIST OF USED LITERATURE AND SOURCES)

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